

POLITICAL SCIENCES

THE UK IN EUROPEAN INTEGRATION AFTER THE BREXIT REFERENDUM AND THE LEAVING PROCESS

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Abstract

The United Kingdom, whose view of European integration has developed differently due to historical, geographical, economic and political reasons, initially did not want to become a member of the European Economic Community (EEC), which is now known as the European Union (EU). After the referendum, the government established under the premiership of Theresa May initiated the process of the United Kingdom's withdrawal from the EU under Article 50 of the Lisbon Treaty.

In this study, the background of Brexit with its historical and current aspects and the progress and completion of the separation process that started after the referendum in our modern period are analyzed.

Keywords: United Kingdom, European Union, Brexit Referendum, Current situation

The unexpected outcome of the Brexit referendum showed that, despite the uncertainty and despair in the first weeks, EU membership should never be seen as the only formula or last hope for foreign policy and democratic development for the UK or any country. It could, even if it was the European Union. Whether the plan of union succeeded or not.

Countries outside the EU (such as Switzerland) with highly developed democracies and economies also exist in the world and are growing in number. In fact, there are countries (Singapore, China, etc.) that do not conform to democratic models in the Western sense and are very successful economically and politically. Therefore, the majority of the British public, who believe that EU membership does more harm than good, expressed their intention to leave in the Brexit referendum and the decision was made to do so.

For the United Kingdom, which has a pluralistic system with a population of immigrants from former colonial countries and a structure of 4 countries (England, Scotland, Wales, Northern Ireland), democratic and economic development among its members Very possible without being (Schnapper, 2020).

The United Kingdom joined the European Communities in 1973, the membership process was approved by a referendum held in 1975. In the 1970s and 1980s, the idea of the United Kingdom's separation from the European Communities was voiced by the members of the Labor Party and the leading names of the trade union. Those who favored leaving the European Union in the 1990s were the newly formed United Kingdom Independence Party (UKIP) and the supporters of the Conservative Party, which was skeptical of the European Union.

European Union However, the commitment of political parties and elites to the transition process and the articulation of a comprehensive vision for the post-EU period is a very urgent and urgent issue. With hundreds of years of democracy and deep-rooted royal institutions, it is not difficult for the UK to achieve and remain

outside the EU and have peaceful and developed relations with European countries.

However, it has been crucial that the issue is considered beyond politics and not turned into a polarizing issue in the 2019 general elections. It should also be noted that Britain has never been a member of the Eurozone and has always been a prominent member of the European Union with its differences. It would be more accurate for the EU to judge it not in terms of superiority but in terms of cultural and political pluralism.

Prime Minister of the time, David Cameron, announced in a manifesto published in 2015 that he would vote for the UK to leave the European Union. Cameron, who was in favor of staying in the European Union, resigned after the decision to leave in the Brexit referendum and was replaced by Theresa May, who called for general elections in less than a year and had a serious loss of votes compared to the previous elections. Theresa May's minority government is backed by the Democratic Unionist Party in key votes.

Six weeks after the Brexit referendum, the Bank of England implemented quantitative easing and lower interest rates. This led to a depreciation of the British pound and higher inflation. It was claimed that the hedge fund and the Brexit referendum survey were responsible for the depreciation of the British pound.

According to the economic researches, it is predicted that the per capita income in the UK will decrease in the medium and long term due to the Brexit referendum. Economists also state that the Brexit referendum will harm the country's economy for two years. Since the Brexit referendum, household income has decreased by an average of 404 British pounds per year, and the gross national product has fallen by between 1.3 and 2.1 percent.

With the Brexit referendum, it is estimated that the number of people coming from the European Economic Area will decrease, and as a result of this decrease, a difficult period will be entered in the UK education system and academic research areas. As of June 2018, the

value of the Brexit-related bill is unknown. It is foreseen that the balances in the UK will change according to the soft or hard implementation of Brexit.

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Theresa May, who took office as the new prime minister of the country, forwarded the withdrawal notification to the relevant institution of the EU within the scope of the Lisbon Treaty, which regulates the exit of the member states from the Union.

Although May reached an agreement on the Withdrawal Agreement with the EU as a result of long negotiations, she could not get the said agreement accepted by the UK parliament (Schnapper, 2020).

Boris Johnson, who took office after May, who resigned from his duty as prime minister due to these developments, stated that he would put an end to the Brexit issue, which gave the country turbulent years in domestic politics. Johnson, who managed to revise the agreement by meeting with the Union again on the Withdrawal Agreement that May had agreed with the EU, left the EU's political mechanisms at the end of January 2020 (Prosser, 2021, pp. 452-454).

With the transition process that started after that, the Trade and Cooperation agreement, which outlines the post-Brexit relations, was signed and the Brexit process was completed with the approval of the said agreement by the UK parliament. As of January 1, 2021, the United Kingdom, which was renewed nationally, took its place in the international arena as an independent voice from the EU (Boyraz, 2021).

Within the scope of this study, first of all, the attitude of the United Kingdom towards European integration will be examined. In this context, it will be mentioned that he sees himself as different from the Continental European countries due to its geography, being an island state and having established an overseas empire in the past.

In order to ensure the trust in the special relationship developed with the USA and the commercial relations with the Commonwealth countries, it will be announced that it does not join the ECSC and EEC, and the different policy it follows for European integration will be revealed (Schnapper, 2020).

Then, the reasons for the UK's interest calculations in the face of the changing world and European conjuncture and its desire to join the EEC will be discussed. In this direction, the struggle of the United Kingdom to become a member of the EEC with the thought of not falling behind the Continental European countries due to the successful economic progress of the EEC will be discussed.

The process of joining the EC of the United Kingdom, which overcame the obstacle on the way to membership with the withdrawal of French President De Gaulle from the political scene, will be examined. Afterwards, the course of relations with the EU after membership and the policies of the ruling administrations towards the Union will be analyzed.

In this context, the Schengen area, which is one of the common policy areas created under the roof of the Union, and the privileged status of the United Kingdom, which has obtained different regulation by refusing to join the economic and monetary union due to the restriction of its sovereignty, within the EU will be discussed.

Then, the process that led David Cameron to the Brexit referendum and the outcome of this referendum, the UK's process of leaving the EU will be examined. In this context, the process of parting ways between London and Brussels will be discussed chronologically and the stages of the Brexit process will be revealed.

After Thatcher came to power, her first agenda in relations with Europe was her country's contribution to the EC budget and, in relation to this, the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). The environment of hunger and famine experienced during the war and the freshness of these pains in the memories of those years pushed the European countries to give priority to the agricultural sector in the new order they created after the war. While this is the case, the agricultural sector has the largest share in the EC budget, and the CAP has been the policy area where the Community has concentrated the most.

The fact that the United Kingdom is the second country that contributes the most to the Community budget, and the asymmetric situation due to the fact that the income from the budget is less than that of other member countries, gave Thatcher years of tension in relations with Europe (Schnapper, 2020).

This asymmetric situation was due to the fact that the UK purchases agricultural products from the Commonwealth countries at cheap prices and the low level of agricultural product trade with the EC countries. In addition, the agricultural sector occupied a small place in the UK economy (Seidel, 2020, pp. 194-196).

In the face of this situation of her country, which is different from other EC countries, Thatcher demanded from the Community to reduce its contribution to the budget, but the members of the Community objected to Thatcher's request.

In particular, France's strict stance on this issue caused the United Kingdom to take a harsh stance in its relations with the EC. Due to the budget issue, the negative course of the UK's relations with other member states and its conflict with the EC did not make Thatcher take a step back, on the contrary, Thatcher remained determined on this issue.

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Referendum discussions for independence in Scotland and Northern Ireland, where a referendum was held to leave the United Kingdom before, arouse repercussions on the agenda. Starting from January 1, 2021, the United Kingdom, which started to draw its own political and economic direction, preferred to move towards becoming a Global Britain, leaving behind its European vision (Schnapper, 2020).

The Global Britain rhetoric, which is frequently expressed by members of the government during the Brexit process, makes it clear that the UK has adopted a more global approach. The United Kingdom, which has drawn its route as to take place all over the world beyond Europe, wants to strengthen its commercial ties around the world by signing bilateral and multilateral trade agreements with many countries.

It is possible for the UK to consider the strengthening of relations with the USA and the free trade agreement that it hopes to sign with the USA as one of the most important gains of Brexit. In addition, it is on the agenda of the United Kingdom to take part in the Anglo-Saxon alliance as the military partner of the USA in order to weaken the power of China, the rising power of the Indo-Pacific region.

In the strategy document titled "Global Britain in a Competitive Age", announced by Prime Minister Johnson in March 2021, the path that the UK will follow in the fields of foreign policy and security after Brexit has been determined. In this context, the document focuses on the United Kingdom's desire to deepen its political and economic relations with the countries of the region by highlighting the Indo-Pacific region.

In this respect, the post-Brexit vision of the United Kingdom bears the signs of developing diplomatic and

commercial relations and gaining economic gain with all the countries of the world by giving priority to the Asia-Pacific countries.

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